

RESISTANCE TO BETA LACTAM ANTIBIOTICS IN GRAM-NEGATIVE MICROORGANISMS, A BRIEF REVIEW*

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*SUMMARY: Resistance mechanisms to β -lactam antibiotics are briefly presented, emphasizing the importance of extended spectrum β -lactamases. In two independent research works from our laboratories, ESBLs were not detected among *Salmonella enterica* serovar Enteritidis and resistance to ampicillin was quite low (out of 878 isolates included in the study, 2.2% were resistant to AMP). As food producing animals are reservoirs of ESBL producing bacteria, antibiotic treatment in veterinary practice has to be selective and the prudent use of antimicrobials is strongly recommended.*

Key words: extended spectrum β -lactamase, bacteria, antibiotics, humans, animals.

HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE

The Penicillin's are the oldest antibiotics introduced in medical practice. A broad range of antibiotics, including penicillin derivatives cephalosporins (I, II, III and IV generation), monobactams, carbapenemes and β -lactam/ β -lactamase inhibitor combinations are available for therapy. All classes of β -lactam antibiotics contain a β -lactam ring in their molecular structures. β -lactam antibiotics act by inhibiting the cell wall synthesis in bacteria. The resistance develops after bacteria produces enzymes termed β -lactamases, which cleave β -lactam ring and prevent antibiotics to bind to penicillin binding proteins (Frye and Jackson, 2013). β -lactamase enzymes are chromosomally mediated or encoded from transferable plasmids and they belong to diverse or genetically similar molecules that are subsequently classified in different groups and derivatives. Widespread application of antibiotics has worsened therapeutic options since bacteria emerged in a whole variety of resistant clones.

Review paper / Pregledni rad

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This work is a short review of enzymes produced by Gram-negative bacteria as a response to β -lactam antibiotics.

Extended-Spectrum β -lactamase (ESBLs) enzymes are important part of defense mechanism in Gram-negative rods. They hydrolyze penicillin's, oxyimino-cephalosporins and oxyimino-monobactam (aztreonam), are often plasmid-mediated and transferable between bacterial species. Classification of major groups of β -lactamases is described in a research work of Bush (2001). According to Ambler molecular classification, ESBL enzymes belong to the group A having serine at the active site. Since there is a growing evidence of new β -lactamases the classification suggested by Bush, Jacoby and Medeiros was adopted. Their classification is based on biochemical properties, molecular structures and sequence of the target genes. In that respect, the ESBL enzymes that hydrolyze oximino-cephalosporins, monobactams and are inhibited by clavulanic acid are classified as a group 2be. The "oldest" ESBL enzyme was found in *E. coli* in 1960. This enzyme was termed TEM-1 because it was discovered in a patient from Greece named Temoniera (Bradford, 2001). It is a plasmid encoded and incorporated into transposon, enabling its successful spread in the environment. The next enzyme, which is frequently found in gram-negative rods, is SHV-1. In *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, it is found on chromosome, while in *E. coli* it is mostly mediated by the plasmid. Most of the ESBLs evolved as derivatives from TEM and SHV enzymes. In SHV variants, amino acid exchanges are most frequently found at position 238 where glycine is replaced by serine. In the variant SHV-5, substitution is attributed to exchange of glutamate for lysine at 240. Both amino acid exchanges are also found in TEM derived ESBLs. Amino acid serine at 238 is important for successful hydrolysis of ceftazidime, while lysine at 240 is critical for hydrolysis of cefotaxime (Bradford, 2001). Phenotype characterization of ESBLs producers is very important and provides the first evidence of the capacity of bacterial enzymes to develop resistance mechanisms.

β -lactamase inhibitors were introduced in therapy owing to their synergistic effect and to enhance therapeutic options. However, inhibitor-resistant β -lactamase has been found from TEM and SHV. The designation TEM-IRT was given to variants that are resistant to the inhibition of following combinations: amoxicillin-clavulanate, ticarcillin-clavulanate and ampicillin-sulbactam. They have emerged in France and some other European countries since 1990. The SHV-10 variant with the inhibitor resistant phenotype was discovered in *E. coli* from urine of a hospitalized diabetic patient, which received amoxicillin-clavulanate therapy (Bradford et al., 2001).

Nowadays, the most frequent mechanism of resistance to β -lactam antibiotics is attributed to new groups of ESBLs - the CTX-M enzymes. They differ genetically from TEM and SHV (40 % of identity) and hydrolyze better cefotaxime than ceftazidime (Bradford, 2001; Chong et al., 2011). These enzymes are widespread in members of *Enterobacteriaceae* and are found in *Salmonella enterica* serotype Typhimurium. The CTX-M family of enzymes is divided into several major groups: CTX-M-1 type, CTX-M-2, CTX-M-8 and Toho 1 and Toho2 enzymes. The most prevalent type is CTX-M-15. It was originally found in *E. coli* and its clonal spread is attributed to the *E. coli* ST131, harboring IncFII plasmid, determining resistance to several classes of antibiotics (Chong et al., 2011). The OXA enzymes belong to the molecular class D and to a functional group 2d (Bush, 2001). These enzymes confer resistance to ampicillin, cephalothin (first generation of cephalosporins) and

they hydrolyze oxacillin and cloxacillin. They are modestly inhibited by clavulanic acid. Variants in OXA genetic group differ from the main ancestor the OXA-10 type, by one, two or more amino acid exchanges. Comprehensive overview of OXA group of enzymes and brief information about other new families of ESBLs could be found in a review paper from Bradford et al. (2001).

Next important group of bacterial enzymes, the AmpC type, is structurally different from ESBLs and according to Ambler classification they belong to the group C. These enzymes confer resistance to the third generation of cephalosporins and to β -lactam/ β -lactamase inhibitor combinations. In fact, they emerged as a consequence of therapy with antibiotic/inhibitor combinations. The resistance is due to the mutational insertions in the promoter region of ampC, leading to constitutive expression of the gene and subsequent extended-spectrum cephalosporin-resistant (ESCs) phenotype (Seiffert et al., 2013).

Carbapenemases are very important enzymes produced by bacteria. They are classified into molecular group A and a subgroup 2f. These enzymes are inhibited with EDTA and contain at least one Zinc atom at the active site. Such molecular construction enhances hydrolysis of a bicyclic β -lactam ring and their catalytic function are different from enzymes that have serin at the active site. Sometimes they are prescribed for therapy in patients infected with highly resistant Gram-negative microorganisms (Livermore 2008). For detailed information about this family of enzymes, a comprehensive review of Queenan and Bush (2007) is recommended for readers.

Resistance of *Salmonella* Enteritidis to beta lactam antibiotics in Southern Bačka and Srem County

In two independent research works, quinolone resistant *Salmonella enterica* serovar Enteritidis (*S. Enteritidis*) was selected to obtain resistotyping. First, a collection of randomly selected *S. Enteritidis* was prepared from stool, food and poultry isolates to perform molecular typing. In this collection, resistance to ampicillin was found in two poultry and three stool isolates. One poultry isolate was resistant only to ampicillin while the other was multiple resistant to several classes of antimicrobials, i.e. resistance was found to ampicillin, cephalothin (a first generation of cephalosporin antibiotics), nalidixic acid (NAL) and tetracycline. Three isolates from human stool were either resistant to ampicillin only or multiple resistant to ampicillin, tetracycline and trimethoprim-sulphamethoxazole (one isolate) and ampicillin, trimethoprim-sulphamethoxazole, NAL and tetracycline (one isolate). Resistance to quinolones was established in 15% of isolates from the collection (Kozoderović et al., 2011). In another work, 878 isolates of *S. Enteritidis* were tested for quinolone resistance. Only 2.2% *S. enteritidis* were found to be resistant to NAL and resistance to β -lactam antibiotics was found in two strains only. One isolate was resistant to ampicillin, trimethoprim-sulphamethoxazole and NAL and one isolate was resistant to ampicillin, cephalothin and trimethoprim-sulphamethoxazole. Because resistance to penicillins and cephalosporins was not significant in NAL resistant strains, we did not determine genes responsible for development of resistance to β -lactams (Kozoderović et al 2012). More comprehensive research regarding β -lactam resistance needs to be done for the members of *Enterobacteriaceae* in the future. Clinical and veterinary isolates of *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella* spp are of particular interest since those bacteria

emerge as multiple resistant in nosocomial infections as well as in animals treated with β -lactam antibiotics.

Resistance to beta lactam antibiotics in food animals-recent findings

Most antimicrobials used for the treatment of animals belong to classes that are also used in human medicine (cloxacillin, gentamicin, ampicillin, amoxicillin etc). The usage of antimicrobial drugs in food producing animals could result in antimicrobial resistance among pathogenic and commensal bacteria in these animals, and the resistant bacteria may then be transmitted to humans through the food chain and increase risk of treatment failures (Petrović et al., 2008; Petrović et al., 2011). Resistance to β -lactam antibiotics, new generation of cephalosporins and also to carbapenems, may cause significant problems in the treatment of nosocomial infections and community or environmentally acquired infections all around the globe (Pitout and Laupland 2008). Person to person transmission in hospital settings and food-borne transmission in the environment and communities is the primary cause of spreading ESBLs (Liebana et al., 2013). Therefore, the emergency of new clones with mobile genetic elements in food animals as well as among humans is extremely important and careful monitoring of resistance patterns through national monitoring programs is warranted (Velhner et al., 2010, Velhner et al., 2012, Liebana et al., 2013). A comprehensive review about dissemination of ESBLs as well as the occurrence of resistant Gram-negative bacteria in livestock industry and its role in food and environmental contamination is published in a work of Seiffert et al. (2013). We briefly present here the research from Germany, Canada, USA and Korea, dealing with ESBLs profiles in food animals. A collection of 22,679 *Salmonella enterica* isolates from Germany, for a period 2003 to 2007, was tested for ESBLs and AmpC production by Rodriguez et al., (2009). These isolates were found in foods, food producing animals, feed, environment, humans or were from unknown sources. All isolates that obtain MIC to ceftiofur of $>4\text{mg/L}$ were further analyzed. Among 16 isolates found to be ESBL positive the *bla*_{CTX-M-1} gene was found in 15 isolates: 9 *Salmonella* Typhimurium (ST), 2 *Salmonella* Anatum, 2 *Salmonella* Paratyphi BdT+, 1 *Salmonella* Infantis and 1 *Salmonella* London. One ST isolate possesses *bla*_{CTX-M-15} gene. Five *Salmonella* Agona and 1 *Salmonella* Kentucky were found to harbor *bla*_{CMY-2} gene. In 2 *Salmonella* Paratyphi BdT+ isolates the *bla*_{TEM-20} gene was found while *bla*_{TEM-52} gene was found in 1 *Salmonella* Paratyphi BdT+ and 1 *Salmonella* Virchow. In this research, the genetic position of the aforementioned genes in mobile genetic elements was studied as well. *Salmonella enterica* and *E. coli* isolates from several European laboratories were selected for molecular typing on their respective plasmids belonging to the incompatibility group IncII. These plasmids are responsible for dissemination of ESBL genes and possess also genes relevant to the virulent potential of Shiga-toxin producing *E. coli*. The following ESBL genes were found in those isolates: *bla*_{CMY-2}, *bla*_{CTX-M-15}, *bla*_{CTX-M-1}, *bla*_{CTX-M-14}, *bla*_{TEM-52}, *bla*_{SHV-12}, *bla*_{TEM-1}. Plasmids were further classified by restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP method) and sorted accordingly, whereas for multilocus sequence typing several alleles were selected to further organize plasmid in different genetic groups. It was found that the source for IncII plasmids and its reservoirs are associated with poultry pathogens such as *Salmonella* spp and *E. coli* (Garcia-Fernandez et al., 2008). Frey and Jackson described resistance patterns in *Salmonella* spp, *E. coli* and *Enterococcus*

spp in the USA. The clonal spread of multiple resistant *Salmonella* carrying IntI1 integrons or IncA plasmids are the most widespread among multiple drug resistant strains (MDR) in the USA. This includes *Salmonella* Typhimurium Definitive Phage Type 104 and *Salmonella enterica* serovar Newport (*S.* Newport). The spread of MDR *S.* Newport is probably associated with antibiotic treatment of cattle with ceftiofur. This clone had a MDR-AmpC phenotype encoded by *bla*_{CMY-2} gene from IncA/C plasmid. Poultry and turkeys may be a source of *Salmonella enterica* serovar Heidelberg. This serovar was found to have IncI1 plasmids with the *bla*_{CMY-2} gene, but MDR phenotype is less frequently expressed. Therapy of neonatal calves and pigs with β -lactams and cepheims is of great concern since these antibiotics are also used in human medicine. In recent years in Canada, plasmid mediated AmpC beta lactamase resistance is more frequent than ESBLs. In that respect, Mataseje et al. (2010) made comparison between different plasmids from *Salmonella* and *E. coli* found in humans, feedlots and water. The isolates included were from different provinces in Canada. The multi locus sequencing strategy combined with the RFLP profiles have shown that genetically similar plasmids are found in *E. coli* and *Salmonella* across Canada. The most frequent clusters were as following: I1, A/C, K/B and the unknown type. Resistance patterns were almost identical in *Salmonella* and environmental *E. coli* isolates and were attributed to the following antimicrobials: ampicillin, amoxicillin/clavulanic acid, ceftiofur and ceftiofur, while in clinical *E. coli* the resistance patterns were related to: ampicillin, cefazolin, ceftiofur and ceftriaxone. In Japan MDR serovars of *Salmonella* spp were also found. The most prevalent among broiler chickens was *S. infantis* exhibiting resistance to 3 or more different classes of antibiotics. For the first time cephalosporin resistance in Japan from food producing animals was reported. The *S.* Senftenberg isolate was isolated from feces of a broiler chicken and particulate isolate carried CTX-M-2 gene (Ishihara et al., 2009). The goal of the research conducted in Korea was to monitor MDR phenotype in nontyphoid *Salmonella* from poultry in 2 provinces and from humans in one province. MDR phenotype was attributed to the following classes of antibiotics: ampicillin, cephalothin, ceftiofur, aztreonam, genatamycin, streptomycin, tetracycline and sulfamethoxazole. In most of the isolates the CTX-M-15 β -lactamase gene prevailed and was associated with MDR and self transferable plasmid (Tamang et al., 2011).

Wild animals have been recognized as a possible source of multiple resistant *E. coli* and resistance to β -lactam antibiotics was found. We have described previously the possible spread of resistant *E. coli* from wild birds and small mammals in nature (Velhner et al., 2012). Several factors play important role in dissemination of resistant bacteria in wildlife. Wild birds that reside close to the urban area and are fed with the waste and sewage are more frequently reservoirs of resistant microorganisms. There have been some seasonal variations for possible spreaders and those parts of Europe with higher population density present significant risk for contaminating the environment comparing to less urban zones. It is very important to prevent our planet from further pollution and to preserve wildlife in the best possible way taking care of their natural habitat and survival.

CONCLUSION

Numbers of reports are dealing with resistance to β -lactam antibiotics and extended-spectrum cephalosporins. Food producing animals are important reservoirs

of infection with ESBL resistant clones. In human medicine, the prudent use of antibiotics is critical, while empirical therapy and easy access to antibiotics present substantial risk in spreading resistant microorganisms in hospitals and community. Therapy with new generations of antibiotics needs to be very restricted and in animal husbandry forbidden or prescribed carefully in order to obtain lower risk of resistance development in bacteria.

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OTPORNOST GRAM-NEGATIVNIH MIKROORGANIZAMA NA BETA LAKTAM ANTIBIOTIKE (Pregled)

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Izvod

U radu je prikazan mehanizam otpornosti gram.negativnih mikroorganizama na β -lactam antibiotike, sa isticanjem značaja širokog spektra β -lactamasa. U dva odvojena ogleda u našoj laboratoriji, ESBLs nije detektovana između *Salmonella enterica* serovar Enteritidis, a otpornost na ampicillin je bila vrlo niska (od 878 izolata, uključenih u istraživanja, svega 2.2% je bilo otporno na AMP). Kako su životinje, od kojih se proizvodi hrana za ljude, rezervoar ESBL, antibiotski tretman u veterinarskoj praksi mora biti selektivan, pa se predlaže vrlo oprezana primena antibiotika.

Ključne reči: širok spetar β -lactamase, bakterija, antibiotici, ljudi, životinje.

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